

Maintenance technologies for roads and its prioritization

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Abstract: The road network is the lifeblood and evidence of the progress of countries, as the road infrastructure has many benefits on the economic and social front. After completing the construction of roads and starting their operation, the roads are exposed to a decrease in structural and functional quality as a result of traffic loads and the influence of weather factors. Therefore, in order to maintain the efficiency of the roads, ensure their quality, and continue to provide the services for which they were established, those roads must be maintained using various maintenance techniques to immediately eliminate various safety risks to ensure the safety of the road and pedestrians on it. The major challenge in keeping highways in good condition is that there will never be enough money to maintain the whole road network. This article discusses the significance of the maintenance of roads and the current problems in the maintenance of roads. The second part discusses the objective of prioritization, and the roles of prioritization in road maintenance. As a result, this article can be used as a reference for future road maintenance and to assist decision makers in allocating limited resources in an efficient and effective manner.

Keywords: Road project, Road maintenance, Prioritization

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Introduction

City roads and related infrastructure are an important part of the country's engineering infrastructure construction and have many economic and social benefits. Under normal circumstances, a good urban road infrastructure can provide convenience for people's life and travel and create a comfortable living environment. Therefore, it is necessary to do a good job in the daily maintenance and management of road projects and eliminate relevant safety hazards and quality problems in a timely manner to ensure that the level of service provided by road engineering projects is maintained. A good and comprehensive road management and maintenance system is required to keep the roads in good condition. Regular and continual maintenance methods and capacity building for roads will keep the route in good condition. The pavement that has been passed by traffic, on the other hand, will face deterioration in quality, both structural and functional. Road maintenance is carried out on a constant basis with sound planning and adequate finance, and the proper form of road maintenance is required to offset the loss in road condition.

Road maintenance is required to ensure the safety, smoothness, and comfort of toll road users. There are several forms of road maintenance handling for roads, with a focus on functional road pavement maintenance to maintain pavement

conditions that give optimal service. As a result, a method for maximizing the evaluation of road pavement conditions is required. Furthermore, due to money limits and time allocation, the road authority requires an adequate maintenance strategy due to the ineffectiveness of road maintenance based on the age of the plan. Maintenance expenditures often account for 15- 70% of the overall value of the finished project [1]. The amount of money spent on maintenance of engineering structures and infrastructures is increasing continuously. Strategic planning includes the development of strategies to attain goals based on the environment in which the company operates and the productive activities of the business [2]. As a result, the broad criteria for strategy formulation try to synthesize strengths, eliminate weaknesses, capitalize on opportunities, and neutralize threats [3].

This article discusses the current problems in maintenance and develops various techniques for maintenance and repair work to provide reference for better maintenance of roads in the future. In addition, it looks for solutions to the problem of lack of maintenance funds, which is often not enough to maintain all roads through conducting the right prioritization.

1. Road Maintenance

Because road networks are an important indicator of the progress of countries and have many benefits on the economic and social front, it is critical to maintain them in order to improve the road network's performance in delivering public services. All activities carried out on local government-managed roadways with the goal of preserving and enhancing their condition in order to keep them usable are referred to as road maintenance. Donnges et al. defined road maintenance as an integrated activity to maintain the structure of local roads at the minimum level of service throughout their design life [4].

Based on the characteristics of the road geometry, the state of the pavement, and the amount of traffic, the examination can be analyzed and evaluated with various project and maintenance approaches. Continually reducing the level of deterioration on the road is the goal of road maintenance in and of itself. Differently applied treatments on the road will have varying maintenance effects, which will result in varied performance over time. Furthermore, the treatment level at which roads are maintained will affect their future performance as well as the total cost of road projects. As a result, to determine which treatment standard is acceptable and economically optimal, the variance in total cost and total road performance with different treatment maintenance standards must be observed [5]. According to Macorig et al. [6], which also suggested that road authorities' priority preventive maintenance over corrective maintenance. In principle, road authorities can efficiently reduce the need for future corrective repair while spending less overall by implementing preventative maintenance.

Five concept areas were used to categorize the road maintenance: the road, the road maintenance, the regular and periodic road maintenance, the winter and summer road maintenance, and the road conditions as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Road maintenance concept areas [7].

1.1. Necessity of Maintenance Technology for Roads

No matter how high the construction quality and level of a project are, it will have a certain service life after it is put into use. Because of the larger load of use, the service life of road projects is often shorter than that specified by the project. Due to the high-speed driving of vehicles and some overloaded trucks, more damage has been done to the main structure of the road engineering, so there will be some road diseases in road engineering projects.

During the use of roads, there are many types of quality and structural problems that may occur, as shown in Figure 2 and Table 1. The most common problem is the cracks on the surface of roads caused by the excessive speeding and overloading of vehicles. Furthermore, when the temperature is too high in summer, the asphalt pavement will absorb a lot of heat, which will cause the rutting in the asphalt layer of the road or the thermal cracks. This requires the maintenance staff of roads to reasonably analyse the specific reasons for the problems, and then choose more targeted, scientific and reasonable technologies for maintenance and repair [8].

Fig. 2: Road Damage types.

Table 1. Frequency of Road Damage [9].

N.	Road Damage	Damage Frequency	
		Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Potholes	2.1000	0.66
2	Rutting	2.4000	0.62
3	Cracking	2.2333	0.63
4	Guardrail damage	2.1667	0.59
5	Drainage deposits	2.2333	0.68
6	Drainage cross section	2.5333	0.63

The appearance and occurrence of these problems will not only affect the appearance of the city but also affect the safety of vehicles and even cause traffic accidents. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the overall level of maintenance and repair of roads and related facilities.

1.2. Common Problems in the Maintenance of Roads

Insufficient Maintenance Quality

The periodic maintenance of road engineering projects and related road infrastructure is very important and critical to whether road engineering projects can perform the function of transportation stably and reliably. Therefore, maintenance and repair work must basically solve the potential problems, including safety hazards, quality problems, and take targeted measures to solve the problems existing in these road engineering projects in a comprehensive way.

At present, there are some obvious problems in the maintenance work of road engineering projects because the overall level of the relevant road maintenance workers in the use of various road maintenance technologies, new materials, and new equipment is still relatively low. So it directly hinders the effective application of new technologies and new materials, as well as the improvement of maintenance technology and the maintenance level of road engineering projects. On the other hand, the professional quality of the staff is uneven and cannot fully meet the requirements in this regard. In addition, there is also a serious problem of negligence in the maintenance and repair of road engineering projects [10]. Generally speaking, the on-site supervision and management staff of engineering projects must assume the roles of supervision and management to ensure that the construction and maintenance of engineering projects meet the maintenance standards and requirements of road engineering projects.

Maintenance Frequency is Low

If the problems existing on the roads are not discovered and reported in time, then this problem cannot be effectively solved. And once the quality problem of the road engineering project occurs and cannot be solved, the damage to the overall structure of the road engineering project will become more and more serious, and even some traffic accidents will be caused [8].

The road traffic staff has to have a rough idea of the system operation status of the road engineering project through on-the-spot surveys or reports from citizens to be able to find the problems on time and make a report to the officials about the road's damage. Then the professional and technical personnel of the highway system will make a scientific and reasonable maintenance plan for the related maintenance and repair work.

Damage Analysis Problem

During the long-term use of municipal road projects and related facilities, some damage may cause deeper damage, and this problem does not appear on the surface [11]. That is to say, the absence of problems on the surface of road projects does not mean that the project has no problem with the deep structure of the city, and the occurrence of these problems will basically involve the joint influence of many related factors, which lead to the deep damage of the urban infrastructure structure and have a serious impact on the system operation of the entire road engineering project. If the deep-seated causes of the structural damage problem are not analyzed but only some superficial problems are solved, and the influencing factors of the problems are not effectively solved, then this problem will recur in a short period of time or even more seriously.

2.3 Relevant Technologies for the Maintenance of Roads

The Quality Control

In the process of maintenance and repair of road engineering projects, it is necessary to strengthen the supervision and management of all relevant building materials and incorporate front-line construction technicians and managers into the management of the entire project. A large part of the construction quality of a project depends on the overall quality of building materials. Therefore, in the management process of building materials, it is necessary to clearly and completely record the storage and use of relevant materials and enter these materials into the management system for use. The selection of relevant building materials must be based on the maintenance and repair needs of the project, and the overall quality and specifications of the building materials must meet the requirements of the current relevant regulations and systems.

Treatment of Structural Problems

It is necessary to study whether the current subgrade is becoming the cause of road damage. In fact, in the process of daily maintenance and repair of road engineering projects, it is relatively rare to deal with subgrade problems. The occurrence of such deep-level road engineering structural problems is a very serious project quality problem. In dealing with and solving such problems, it is necessary to cooperate with the construction unit of the road project and the project design unit. When it is found that there is a serious quality problem in the subgrade structure of the project, Formulate scientific and reasonable construction plans must be based on the actual situation of the problem for high-level, high-

quality maintenance. In addition, for those road sections that have been fully demonstrated and cannot be put back into use through maintenance and repair, re-construction must be carried out to prevent the expansion of the problem and its impact on traffic safety.

Maintenance Time

Time is one of the most important parameters influencing road maintenance and its cost. The discovery of road issues at a late stage is caused by the lack of monitoring activities of the state of the roads while they are in use as well as delays in reporting to the appropriate authorities. If a road problem is not identified and the required maintenance is not done in a timely manner, it could result in further damage and the formation of new problems with the road structure, raising the cost of maintenance. If so, planning ahead for a while is necessary to prevent the issue, which will allow for an increase in quality while lowering maintenance costs.

Fig. 3: The severity of road distress increases over time.

Maintenance of Drainage Facilities

When maintaining the drainage facilities of road engineering projects, it is first necessary to determine whether the drainage facilities of road engineering projects have the problem of sewage discharge obstruction. Once it is found that there is a drainage obstacle in the drainage system, the relevant municipal management staff will further combine the specific conditions of the road section to determine whether the drainage system can return to normal drainage after removing the blocked debris. If the inner diameter of the drainage device of the road infrastructure project is too small due to the original design plan, which hinders the drainage function of the road project, then this problem must be effectively recorded and reported to the superior management personnel to comprehensively analyze whether the drainage structure needs to be reconstructed. Especially in the period of heavy precipitation, professional supervisors can be dispatched to the site for investigation. When it is found that the drainage cannot be drained in time, the expansion of the drainage channel needs to be completed.

2. Road Maintenance Prioritization

Development faces a major obstacle represented by the existence of a gap between the funds needed for infrastructure projects and the budget allocated or available. Moreover, there is an increase in human requirements for infrastructure projects to facilitate their activities and meet their needs, especially with the significant increase in population density and the high level of luxury. However, the money and time that governments have are usually limited, which restricts the development of the country's infrastructure in general and the road network in particular. This in turn leads to the need to establish an evaluation and selection process for the nominated projects that will be implemented, which is not an easy process due to the need to take several factors and criteria into consideration to determine the best projects for implementation [12].

Prioritization is the process of comprehensive study and careful analysis to classify the projects to be implemented, determine the optimal alternatives, and select the important projects so that they are compatible with limited financial resources and development requirements as optimally as possible. According to that definition, it might be argued that

setting priorities for road maintenance is an important first step in deciding which roads need to be maintained. The objective of conducting prioritization is to evaluate the identified projects and to rank them in order of importance [13]. When it comes to road maintenance, the resources that are available do not match the requirements of the roads that need to be maintained. Realizing the existence of a disparity in the importance of some roads over others and their varying impacts on the service level, and due to limited resources, prioritization can be adopted as a solution to prioritize planned maintenance work for roads. In this situation, the decision-makers can maintain the most important roads by evaluating them in accordance with specific standards in order to best utilize the limited resources while achieving optimal results as possible.

2.1. Road Maintenance Prioritization Methods

Each prioritization method has unique procedures that are reflected in the order in which an alternative set is ranked. There are typically four steps that are used in the prioritization process [13]. As explained below,

1. Decide on the project evaluation criteria.
2. Create performance metrics to determine whether a project complies with those requirements.
3. In some way, combine the scores for each performance metric.
4. Determine the priority of the projects and Rank them.

Due to the various considerations and circumstances, no method can be used in every situation or location.

The methods range from the straightforward to the intricate and from the simple to the complex. Hudson et al. [14] put forth six categories of prioritization methods, which are: 1) simple subjective ranking based on judgments; 2) ranking based on parameters; 3) ranking based on parameters with economic analysis; 4) optimization by mathematical programming model on a year-by-year basis; 5) optimization using a marginal cost effectiveness approach; and 6) comprehensive optimization by mathematical programming model.

Because the last three methods are comparable, the six methods in this study can be simplified into four methods as summarized below.

Subjective Judgment-Based Ranking

There is no analytical instrument employed in this method; instead, it only relies on the experience and judgments of the decision-makers in choosing the routes to be maintained. As a result, the priorities that are established often have bias and are inconsistent, which is not ideal. By establishing "high, medium, and low" cost-effectiveness indicators, subjective judgment-based ranking entails a subjective evaluation of how every project relates to achieving objectives [15].

Parameter-Based Ranking

Although this technique is quick, easy to apply, and straightforward, the outcomes might not be ideal. In the field of road maintenance, various priority evaluation methods are used to provide priority rating scores based on numerical composite indices, such as the road condition index, the defects rating index, the maintenance need index, and the unreliability condition index. However, the majority of those plans merely address the state of the pavement [14]. If the ranking is based on multiple criteria or factors rather than just one, then this strategy can boost the transparency of the prioritization process.

Ranking Based on Parameters with Economic Analysis

Due to its relative simplicity, this strategy is the most widely used method in the prioritization process. The benefit-to-cost ratio, life cycle financial estimation, or the effectiveness of cost can all be employed as decision-making tools in this approach. In reality, it converts all maintenance aspects to comparable monetary values before comparing various projects using an economic index to determine which is more advantageous [16]. However, it might be challenging to quantify all pertinent project impacts in monetary terms. Thus, a thorough investigation of this strategy is required.

Optimization

This technique is highly difficult and frequently takes the longest. On the other hand, it has the benefit of generating the best decision possible, one that maximizes the advantages and minimizes the disadvantages [14]. Additionally, the optimization method takes into account both space and time (past and future) (entire network). In order to achieve this, road segments are divided into various condition groups based on elements including pavement quality and traffic volume.

The road network's percentage in each condition category at various times illustrates how well the road network has performed throughout time. The optimization technique aims to increase performance criteria while simultaneously decreasing expenses and the network's weaknesses. The selection of functional requirements, performance variables, road condition classifications, specifying alternative maintenance strategies, and the creation of the mathematical model are necessary steps to achieve these goals.

3. Conclusion

The high quality, high level and safe operation of road engineering projects are very important to ensure the travel of the people and the normal operation of the entire city. During the long-term use of road engineering projects, relevant maintenance and repairs must be done. As far as possible, some basic road engineering problems will be solved and dealt with at the initial stage.

Prioritization assists responsible authorities and decision-makers in efficiently and effectively allocating resources for road projects' maintenance so that roads can remain in the best possible condition. In addition, prioritization is also an essential component of road maintenance, particularly when funds are scarce.

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